

Burnout: Comparative Study between House Officers and Final Year Medical Students across Gender and Sector

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ABSTRACT

Background & Objectives: The purpose of this study was to compare the burnout in house officers and medical students of final year in public and private sector of Lahore. Additionally the current study aims to find out the gender differences and sector wise differences on the variable of burnout.

Study design: Cross-sectional study.

Place & duration of study: Public and private medical colleges and hospitals of Lahore, Pakistan. The duration of the study was from March 2017 to Dec 2017.

Methods: The sample of 240 participants (120 final year MBBS students & 120 house officers) having age range of 22 to 25 years of age was selected from public and private sector. For assessment purpose demographic form and the abbreviated nine items inventory "abbreviated Maslach Burnout Inventory (aMBI)" was used for the measurement of burnout among medical students and house officers.

Results: Findings of current study revealed more "depersonalization" ($t(238) = 3.14, p < .05$) and more "personal accomplishment" ($t(238) = 4.24, p < .05$) on the sub-scales of burnout in house officers as compared to the final year medical students. No significant gender differences were revealed. Further sector wise analysis showed interesting findings that participants from public sector showed more "personal accomplishment" ($t(238) = .029, p < .05$) than their counterparts from private sector, but revealed no significant differences on other subscales of burnout of "emotional exhaustion" and "depersonalization".

Conclusion: This study highlighted that house officers are suffering more from "depersonalization" which indicates lack of commitment, distancing from patients, and handling of the patients as inanimate objects. This study also revealed that public sector house officers and final year students showed more personal accomplishment which represents high sense of efficacy, commitment and capacity to involve, change and improve than their counter parts in private sector.

Keywords: Burnout, House Officers, Medical Students, Gender differences

INTRODUCTION

Burnout is a measure of exhaustion at physical and psychological level and mental anguish catalyzed largely by occupational and professional demands. Burnout is mostly comprised of increased level of Emotional Exhaustion (EE), Depersonalization (DP), and decreased level of Personal Accomplishment (PA). Burnout is commonly found in individuals working in those fields which serve humanity, especially doctors that can influence their job satisfaction and patient dealing. Medicine is a fundamentally challenging profession, one that seems likely to leave many medical professionals at risk for burnout.

Burnout was originally thought to come later in a medical field, after idealism has given way to practicality, and the allure with medical practice is substituted by routine. The cause of burnout is multifaceted and ambiguous; however it is becoming gradually more evident that many medical students start to face burnout in medical school years, with pervasiveness of 49% in medical students in American medical students and in Australia it ranges from 28 to

61%.¹

Medical school years are challenging and previous research literature suggests that there are a lot of factors which play a significant role in increasing the stress level and mental health conditions in medical students. These contributing factors might be the academic stress and educational arrears, gender, events in personal life, learning atmosphere and frequent exposure to the human suffering and misery in the clinical settings. Cecil and colleagues (2014) conducted research in UK found out that burnout is present in undergraduate medical students.² Results also revealed that gender, educational institute, and year of study also appear to influence the morbidity of burnout.

Recent research literature estimates the high prevalence of burnout across globe. It is reported in around 40% of American doctors in general and as high as 76% in internal medicine.^{2, 3, 4} A study in Pakistan showed an emotional exhaustion score of 47% among the doctors working in Services Institute of Medical Sciences, which is quite alarming.⁵ Similar pattern was observed in another study in Rawalpindi tertiary care hospital, that dissatisfaction of working environment was 44.5%, dissatisfaction due to working hours and work load was 39.4% and 42.5%.⁶

The high prevalence of burnout in medical profession is

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problematic as it may erode professionalism, contribute to medical errors, leads to suicidal ideation and attrition, and be a factor in substance abuse and relationship difficulties. Distress during medical school years can lead to burnout, with harmful consequences, particularly if burnout persists to house job and then residency. Although the doctors are facing increased propensity to retire early because of the workload and decrease in job satisfaction, burnout seems to be less common in the category of senior doctors as compared to early career doctors. As medical students shift from most didactic-filled schedule to that one which focuses on patient care, it leads to high level of stress.^{7,8} Research literature highlights the need to focus attention on burnout phenomenon during last medical school years especially during their internship as house officers as they are more indulged in clinical rotation and patient interaction, it could lead to suboptimal care of patient and decline in concern for personal health and mental well being. We therefore undertook this study to investigate the burnout in final year medical students and house officers of public and private sector of Lahore.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The sample comprised of 240 participants (120 females & 120 males). The data was collected through purposive sampling which is non-probability sampling technique. For sample half participants were final year students of MBBS and other half were house officers from private and public sector medical colleges and hospitals in the city of Lahore.

Measures

Demographic and Personal Information Form

Demographic information was obtained through form, which aims to gain information relevant to the participant's age, gender, education, parent's education, and their monthly income.

Abbreviated Maslach Burnout Inventory (aMBI)

Burnout is measured with the Maslach Burnout Inventory by means of three sub-scales: *emotional exhaustion* (EE), *depersonalization* (DP), and *personal accomplishment* (PA). Various versions of the MBI exist. The Abbreviated MBI version comprised of total nine items, three in each subscale. Abbreviated Maslach Burnout Inventory aMBI items coded as 0 for "never" to 6 for "every day"; There are three separate components of this burnout inventory, which are given below:-

- i. *Emotional exhaustion*: In this component items described the reduced energy level, job enthusiasm, emotional and cognitive distancing from the job.
- ii. *Depersonalization*: The items included in this components measures the cynicism, lack of engagement, distancing from patients, and

treatment of the patients as inanimate objects.

- iii. *Personal accomplishment*: This component measures a sense of efficacy and effectiveness, commitment, and capacity to involve, change and improve.

The lower scores in personal accomplishment and higher scores on emotional exhaustion and depersonalization are indicators of higher burnout.⁹

PROCEDURE

The participants were selected from four medical colleges (2 public & 2 private sectors) and four hospitals (2 public & 2 private sectors) in the city of Lahore. Consent was taken from the authorities of these educational and health care institutes and later consent was taken from the participants on the individual level during data collection. The demographic and Maslach Burnout Inventory were administered individually on medical students of final year and house officers.

SCORING AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The statistical Package for Social sciences (SPSS, version 19.0) was used to analyze the data. The descriptive statistics and t-test was used for assessing the differences on the variables of burnout between house officers and final year MBBS students, across gender and sector.

RESULTS

Note; $t(238) = 4.24$ $p < .05$ for Personal Accomplishment and $t(238) = 3.14$, $p < .05$ for Depersonalization indicate significant differences in house officers and final year medical students.

Statistical analysis in Table 1 revealed that $p > .05$ indicates that there is no significant difference in the level of Emotional Exhaustion in the house officers and final year medical students.

Findings in Table 2 revealed that $t(238) = -.071$, $p > .05$ indicates that there was no significant gender difference in the level of Emotional Exhaustion. Similar results of no gender differences were revealed as $t(238) = 3.14$, $p > .05$ for Depersonalization and $t(238) = .200$, $p > .05$ for Personal Accomplishment sub-scale.

Note; $t(238) = 2.19$, $p < .05$ indicates that there is significant difference in the level of Personal Accomplishment in the government and private sector

Analysis of results in the Table 3 highlight that $t(238) = -.139$, $p > .05$ indicates that there was no significant difference in the level of Emotional Exhaustion in government and private sector and similar pattern was visible by $t(238) = -1.047$, $p > .05$ for Depersonalization.

Table 1. Differences between House Officers and Final Year Medical Students on Subscales of Burnout Scale

	Groups	N	M	SD	t	df	p
Emotional	HOs	120	9.76	4.41	-1.815	238	.071
Exhaustion	Final year students	120	10.85	4.81	4.81		
Depersonalization	HOs	120	7.06	5.05	3.14	238	.002
	Final year students	120	5.10	4.62			
Personal accomplishment	Hos	120	13.99	3.03	4.24	238	.000
	Final year students	120	12.07	3.90			

Table 2. Gender Differences on Subscales of Burnout Scale

	Groups	N	M	SD	t	df	p
Emotional	Males	120	9.76	4.41	-1.815	238	.071
Exhaustion	Females	120	10.85	4.61			
Depersonalization	Males	120	6.10	5.18	.078	238	.938
	Females	120	6.05	4.69			
Personal accomplishment	Males	120	12.73	3.94	-1.286	238	.200
	Females	120	13.33	3.25			

Table 3. Differences between Private and Public Sector on Subscales of Burnout Scale

	Groups	N	M	SD	t	df	p
Emotional	Government	120	10.26	4.42	-.139	238	.890
Exhaustion	Private	120	10.35	4.87			
Depersonalization	Government	120	5.75	5.14	-1.047	238	.296
	Private	120	6.41	4.70			
Personal accomplishment	Government	120	13.54	3.40	2.193	238	.029
	Private	120	12.52	3.76			

DISCUSSION

Medical students encounter a significant amount of stress throughout their medical training.¹⁰ This is a foreseeable and important part of being a medical student: it motivates and stimulates learning among medical students. However, chronic, intense stress can arouse feelings of fear, uselessness, anger, incompetence and guilt. If it is not handled appropriately, stress and burnout can lead to high levels of depression, substance abuse, relationship problems, anxiety, and suicide.¹¹

The current study compared the burnout between final year medical college students and house officers who are doing their internship in hospital setting. This study further compares prevalence of burnout in public and private sector colleges and hospitals in Lahore. For deeper analysis gender differences were also analyzed. The results in Table 1 indicate the high “depersonalization” one of the aspect of burnout in house

officers than final year medical students. It is presumed that burden of clinical work and tough timing increased during house job instead of their student's life. Similar trend of high burnout was found out by Al- Dabai and colleagues (2013) among medical residents in Malaysia. Their findings also revealed that most common source of job stress was “fear of making mistakes” during training in clinical setting.¹² In the current study, findings also revealed that the “emotional exhaustion” was more prevalent in the medical students as compared to house officers but that difference was not statistically significant. These findings about this minor difference are steady with a current systematic evaluation on burnout in medical students, and suggest that many medical students are vulnerable of, or are previously victim of burnout well before they meet the criteria as medical doctors.¹ Interestingly house officers showed significantly high “personal accomplishment” as

compare to medical students of final year.

The results in Table 2 revealed no gender differences on burnout. These findings are supported by the research work of Linzer and colleagues (2002) found no gender differences in physicians of Netherland and latest research work by Aftab and colleagues (2016) in Lahore found that gender was not associated with the burnout.^{13,14}

In Pakistan, working conditions and professional environment is almost same for both males and females which might be the factor for no gender differences. Although other factors like lack of social support from colleagues, limited delegation of power, lower pay back and poor doctor patient relationship are associated with burnout.^{14,15}

Further analysis of the variable of burnout across private and public sector in Table 3 highlights the difference between both sectors on “personal accomplishment”. Public sector final year medical students and house officers showed higher level of personal accomplishment as compared to their counterparts in private sector. It might be the reason that more workload gives more exposure and work experience as compared to private sector. There were no significant differences visible on the “emotional exhaustion” and “depersonalization”. Overall these findings revealed that emotional exhaustion and depersonalization which are two aspects of burnout are equally prevalent in public and private sector as supported by the findings of research conducted by Aslam and colleagues (2013) in Bahawalpur that workload and night shifts were significant factors playing role in stress level of doctors in both sectors.¹⁶ Although the present study offers an improved understanding of the burnout faced by the medical students and house officers of public and private sectors in Lahore, Pakistan; yet there is a room for more in intensive and in depth research work on the predictors of burnout among doctors of public and private hospitals across the country.

CONCLUSION

Medical profession is thought to be one of the most challenging field as it requires both physical and psychological involvement of doctors. Factors that lead to stress among medical professionals are long working hours, night shifts, hurdles in grooming and polishing their medical skills and lack of facilities. Our study highlights the need to address the issue of burnout in medical field. A peaceful and contented environment must be given to doctors that is crucial to improve the performance in there professional field. There is a need to develop policy at national level in Pakistan for medical professionals in order to guard their rights and provide them a better working environment.

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